

Deliverable N°6.4

Title: setting up of the website

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Actual submission date: M6

Work package: WP6 / Task: 6.4

Work package leader: CIHEAM-IAMB

Deliverable leader: CIHEAM-IAMB

Version: Draft

Dissemination level	
Public	x
Classified, as referred to Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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1. Introduction

MyPack project aims to move forward with innovative packaging in terms of market replication to reduce waste in food and packaging materials and its negative impacts on the environment.

To complete the visual image and make the information about the project in general, but also about its 5 main work packages in detail more available to the general and informed public, the project website (D6.4) was created.

The website's layout, content and entire development process will be outlined in detail in the following chapters.

2. Website development process

Within MyPack project governance, the Work Package (WP) 6 on Dissemination activities tasked with developing the project website.

As a main digital communication tool, the first (1.0) version of the MyPack website was already launched at the beginning of May 2018.

The first version of the website will allow WP6 to measure the interest of the project target groups (identified in deliverable 6.5.) in the project in general terms (www.mypackfood.eu).

3. Website layout and content

The first version of the website is user-friendly and allows users to access all the necessary details about the MyPack project in only a few clicks. The website's language was intentionally created in a less technical manner to allow all MyPack target groups to grasp the main idea behind the project and catch up with the latest project developments without any additional technical knowledge. Indeed, the website also refers visitors interested in finding more about the technical details to the right content pages and contact persons.

In the following lines, the layout of the MyPack website will be presented together with an explanation of its main features/sections.

3.1. Homepage

The homepage is clear and offers users the possibility to immediately learn more about the MyPack project without clicking for additional content. Next to this, the homepage allows users to be informed about the different technologies used in the framework of the project and follow the latest news and the upcoming relevant events.

The homepage provides an opportunity to connect with the institutions of MyPack project partners and outlines the contact details of the responsible persons who can be contacted for additional information.

3.2. About section

The **About section** contains more information about the MyPack project and the opportunity to connect with the project through different mediums and the main objectives, including detail regarding project work packages, impact, the used packaging technologies, deliverables, and an overview of the partners involved.

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Overview

MyPack "Best markets for the exploitation of innovative sustainable food packaging solutions" is a four-year project started on November 1st, 2017 and funded by the Horizon 2020 program (Grant Agreement Number 774265).

The goal of MyPack is to support the market introduction of innovative packaging in order to reduce both food and packaging waste and their negative influence on the environment. In the 27 European countries, 89 million tons of food waste is produced each year, which means that Europeans throw away 20% of the food they buy.

Packaging waste is also produced by the ton, and the recovery rate varies between 50 and 98%, the recycling rate between 50 and 79%.

An important parameter for evaluating packaging is its optimal environmental impact. For such a concept to success, the consumers also need to participate. Information, awareness raising, and dissemination of the advantages are key elements in this.

That is why MyPack aims to include the various expectations from different consumer groups related to product sustainability, handling, and product safety and quality in the project. New packaging can be adapted to many different consumer expectations. MyPack strives to find the best possible products and the best possible market for the commercial development of new packaging technologies.

More information and updates on project activities are available on MyPack website and social media channels:

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Home /mypack/Sustainable Packaging Solutions Objective
Objective

MyPack will provide general guidelines to select the best market for a new technology. These guidelines will provide tools and methodologies to packaging and manufacturing industries, for an appropriate commercial development strategy taking into account:

- **The environmental efficiency (direct impacts of packaging, food waste impacts, optimized recycling, preserved consumer health).**
- **The consumer adoption.**
- **An optimized industrial feasibility.**

These general objectives will be developed for two groups of packaging technologies:

- **PROMOTE THE DEVELOPMENT OF BIOPLASTIC PACKAGING;**
- **PROMOTE THE COMMERCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF BIODEGRADABLE AND COMPOSTABLE PACKAGING**
- **PROMOTE THE COMMERCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF PACKAGING FROM RENEWABLE RESSOURCES**
- **PROMOTE THE DEVELOPMENT OF ELABORATED (HIGH BARRIER AND ACTIVE) PACKAGING TECHNOLOGIES.**

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Project Coordinator: Christophe Cotillon (ACTIA)

MyPack has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no.774265

MyPack project is structured in 8 Work Packages, developed to help it to deliver its results:

WP1: Specifications from industry, technical macroeconomic and regulatory barriers

The main objective of WP1 is to collect new specifications from industry as well as to identify technical, macroeconomic and regulatory barriers, focusing on food packaging. WP1 is expected to describe the current situation along the whole technological chain including:

- Task 1.1: Specifications from packaging industries.
- Task 1.2: Specifications (technical and marketing) from agro-industries.
- Task 1.3: Specifications (technical and marketing) from Retailers.
- Task 1.4: Macroeconomic and regulatory barriers, legislation and standards, including end of life solution.

WP2: Specifications from consumers

Main objectives of WP2 are consisting in: (i) Mapping target populations for new and improved packaging, (ii) Mapping consumer-level requirements for product packaging optimization, (iii) Validating new packaging potential with a focus on local circumstances, (iv) Collating design specifications.

- Task 2.1: Identify target populations.
- Task 2.2: Acceptability of packaging technologies.
- Task 2.3: Making technologies acceptable.
- Task 2.4: Preferred food markets for each packaging innovation.

WP3: Food waste data, and environmental assessment

The objective of WP3 is to identify product-packaging-market clusters enabling the definition of 'fit for packaging' purpose on a system perspective and the eco-efficiency assessment of such packaging by means of the combination of LCA and LCC methodologies.

- Task 3.1: Extending the knowledge on food waste data in order to prioritize food categories and initial leverage points for packaging innovation.
- Task 3.2: Shelf life / Food waste relationship.
- Task 3.3: LCA and LCC.
- Task 3.3.1: General study on a large series of typical food packaging products.
- Task 3.3.2: Clustering of high impact / low impact packaging (introducing food waste and landfill) ponderations the resulting classification will be improved.
- Task 3.3.3: LCA and LCC scenario analysis and new procedures to take into account complex relationships between shelf life and food waste.
- Task 3.3.4: LCA and LCC scenario analysis and new procedures to take into account the overall positive effect of using biodegradable materials.
- Task 3.3.5: detailed case studies comparative LCA and LCC for (i) bio-plastics, (ii) elaborated packaging technologies.

WP4: Packaging innovations : Industrial feasibility, functionality, chemical inertia, end life feasibility

The main objective of WP4 is consisting in overcoming the barriers identified for the different types of packaging using the data collected in the project.

- Task 4.1: Elaborated packaging technologies.
- Task 4.1.1: SiOx technology.
- Task 4.1.2: Biodegradable packaging.
- Task 4.1.3: SiOx technology.
- Task 4.2: Breathing technology.
- Task 4.3: Antimicrobial packaging.
- Task 4.1.4: Nanolayer technology.
- Task 4.2.
- Task 4.2.1: biodegradable packaging.
- Task 4.2.2: Renewable PLA based packaging.
- Task 4.2.3 Renewable PEF based packaging.
- Task 4.3: End life feasibility, functional and migration properties.

WP5: Optimization and exploitation plan

The main objective of WP5 is consisting in exploiting the results of MyPack thanks to two different approaches: (i) a direct and pragmatic exploitation of the technologies by the end users partners in connection with technology providers to access to the market, (ii) an exploitation of the technologies developed through MyPack results.

- Task 5.1: Exploitation potential of existing packaging technologies.
- Task 5.2: Design of improved technologies, considering industrial, distribution, marketing, consumer and LCA/ LCC specifications.
- Task 5.3: Realization of optimized pre series packaging.
- Task 5.4: Testing and consumer acceptability of optimized packaging.
- Task 5.5: Exploitation of "MyPack optimized" packaging technologies.

WP6: Dissemination activities

WP6 acts as the main interface between the project and the outside world, industrialists and academics playing a role in the value network underpinning methods to overcome the barriers to market uptake of many promising food packaging technologies. Towards this goal, the following tasks aim at making the project work widely known, establishing links with related ongoing research initiatives, managing the foreground knowledge and protecting it as appropriate, exploring and assessing emerging application areas, and setting the foundations for future commercial exploitation and opportunities.

- Task 6.1: Dissemination and Communication activities.
- Task 6.2: Communication about the Set of guidelines.
- Task 6.3: Knowledge and Data Management.
- Task 6.4: Stakeholders evaluation workshops.
- Task 6.5: Sustainability of MyPack activities.

WP7: Project management

This WP aims at (i) defining and maintaining the decisional and operational framework, and (ii) making clear to all participants how are the activities monitored and controlled, and how the results are assessed and reported throughout the project life cycle.

- Task 7.1: Strategic Decision Making.
- Task 7.2: Operational Management.
- Task 7.3: Risk Management.
- Task 7.4: Innovation Management and Impact Assessment.

WP8 - Ethics requirements

This WP defines and monitors the ethics requirements that the participants/partners of MyPack project must comply with.

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Impact

MyPack project is designed to generate maximum impact right from the outset and in the long-run, by moving forward innovative packaging in terms of material replication and better consumer acceptance.

In specific, MyPack project aims to generate the following impacts:

- Reduce waste in both food and packaging materials, and its negative impacts on the environment. Concretely, the objective is to increase by 20% the use of biodegradable and packaging from renewable resources, also to increase by 20% the use of elaborated packaging technologies in food applications in Europe at horizon 2025.
- Strengthening the European food value chain through continued support to product quality, contributing to consumer trust and increased consumption.
- Strengthening of the EU's position in manufacturing: improving competitiveness as well as opportunities for growth, diversification and job creation for the EU food and packaging sector in general, and SMEs in particular.
- Support for the transition from a linear to a circular economy. MyPack will provide guidelines as macroeconomic tools to skip the barriers on select the best geographical location with a global coherence between innovation needs and environmental expectations for the best development of a sustainable technology.
- Provide guidelines that will encourage the market to target before expanding the use of technology, and enable new technology providers to understand all barriers to market access, be they regulatory, technical, industrial, or consumer acceptance.

The development of MyPack technologies will take place in three stages: (i) direct exploitation will enable high packaging technologies to rapidly find end-users; (ii) activities and creation of these technologies will allow to meet barriers to market access; (iii) the use of the MyPack tools will allow the used packaging.

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MyPack project is supported to produce the following Deliverables

MyPack project is supported to produce the following Deliverables:

Work Package 1 - Identification: EU industry, to which the technology and regulatory horizon

- 1. General guidelines, barriers and opportunities identified in industrial, macroeconomic, regulatory, political domain.
- 2. Specific report on fresh use agrifood products.
- 3. Specific report on sustainable food.
- 4. Specific report on Organic products.

Work Package 2 - Identification: Fresh consumers

- 1. General guidelines, barriers and opportunities identified in consumer.
- 2. Specific report on fresh use agrifood products.
- 3. Specific report on sustainable food.
- 4. Specific report on Organic products.

Work Package 3 - Road maps: EU, and macroeconomic assessment

- 1. General guidelines on macroeconomic opportunities, and EU's global position of fresh industry.
- 2. Fresh use agrifood.
- 3. Sustainable consumer: need for regulation, and fresh use agrifood products.
- 4. Packaging and food consumption in EU.
- 5. Report on the approach to EU.
- 6. Report on the approach to the EU.

Work Package 4 - Packaging alternatives: Market feasibility, Sustainability, Political, economic, and EU's feasibility

- 1. Report on market feasibility: political, legal, and consumption related F&O, packaging technologies.
- 2. Report on market feasibility: political, legal, and consumption related F&O, packaging technologies.

Work Package 5 - Identification and exploitation plan

- 1. Report on F&O: exploitation of packaging technologies.
- 2. Report on F&O: exploitation of packaging technologies.
- 3. Report on F&O: exploitation of packaging technologies.
- 4. Report on F&O: exploitation of packaging technologies through the EU's regulatory approach.
- 5. Exploitation plan and business plan.

Work Package 6 - Dissemination activities

- 1. Communication and Dissemination materials.
- 2. Report on dissemination and exploitation of the results.
- 3. European project communication activities.
- 4. Report on sustainability: MyPack solution and results.
- 5. Stakeholder management.

Work Package 7 - Impact management

- 1. Impact framework.
- 2. MyPack Impact Management Plan.
- 3. MyPack Impact Management Plan: Long-term impact monitoring.

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Home MyPack Sustainable Packaging Solutions Partners

Partners

MyPack is coordinated by 18 partners involving academic, scientific, and industrial world-wide leading SMEs.

Participant Logo/Name	Acronym	Country
1. ASSOCIATION OF CONVENTION CONTRACTORS FOR SUSTAINABLE PACKAGING	ACTIA	France
2. CONSERVATOIRE NATIONAL DES ARTS ET METIERS	CNAM-PSMA	France
3. WIRTSCHAFTSUNIVERSITÄT WIEN	WU	Austria
4. UNIVERSITÀ DEL SALENTO	UNSA	Italy
5. UNIVERSITÄT WÜRZBURG	UNW	Germany
6. UNIVERSITEIT VAN LIEDERDE	UNL	Netherlands
7. UNIVERSITÄT ZÜRICH	UNZH	Switzerland
8. UNIVERSITÄT SAKS	UNSAK	Czechia
9. UNIV. DI PADOVA	UNIPD	Italy
10. RWTH AACHEN UNIVERSITY	RWTHA	Germany
11. UNIVERSITAT DE VALÈNCIA	UNIV	Spain
12. UNIVERSITÀ DEL SALENTO	UNSA	Italy
13. UNIVERSITEIT VAN LIEDERDE	UNL	Netherlands
14. UNIVERSITÄT WÜRZBURG	UNW	Germany
15. UNIVERSITÄT ZÜRICH	UNZH	Switzerland
16. UNIVERSITÄT SAKS	UNSAK	Czechia
17. UNIVERSITÄT SAKS	UNSAK	Czechia
18. UNIVERSITÄT SAKS	UNSAK	Czechia

AVAILABILITY OF MATERIALS FOR SUSTAINABLE PACKAGING

UNIVERSITÄT WÜRZBURG

UNIVERSITÄT ZÜRICH

UNIVERSITÄT SAKS

3.3. Publications section

The publication section promotes the scientific publication to ensure the project's maximum impact.

3.4. News and Events section

News & Events section provides the users with an overview of the latest project news, upcoming relevant events and press releases published as a part of the overall MyPack media outreach. This aims at showcasing activities organized or which partners participate in and features updates on the project activities.

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News

May 16, 2018 / Events/News
Open workshop & annual Consortium meeting 2018 in Hohenheim University, Germany

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3.5. communications section

This section presents the videos, pictures, factsheet & posters. It aims at presenting the activities conducted and developed during the project's lifetime.

3.6. Contact us section

The contact us section allows users to contact the project management (e.g. WP7) and/or communication team (e.g. WP6) through the designated e-mail addresses.

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Contact us

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4. Future developments

The project website has been designed to allow future developments and ensure its dynamic evolution throughout the project duration. In this regard, WP6 will consider the statistics of the website and page views to assess and plan future developments on the website. Furthermore, the website views and impacts analysis will allow WP6 to understand the web visitors' interests.

In addition, the website's future technical and design updates will aim to address key steps of the project, e.g. dissemination and communication of the project, trial and obtained results.

WP6 will involve the WP leaders and project partners for contribution and inputs when planning future developments.

